

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE EFFECT OF ADHERENCE TO THE CONTROLS OF
PATIENCE AND COMMITMENT BY THE PARAMEDIC ON
THE FEELING OF COMFORT AND SATISFACTION AMONG
RECIPIENTS OF THERAPEUTIC SERVICES**

¹Saeed Ahmed alzahrani , ²Ahmed Majhoul Alzahrani , ³Abdullah Khdran Alzahrani ,
⁴Sultan saeed alzahrani, ⁵Saleh Ibrahim Alzahrani , ⁶Waleed Ahmad Alzahrani , ⁷Ahmed
Ibrahim Alzahrani , ⁸Aziz kader Alghamdi , ⁹Khodran Abdulkhaliq Alzahrani

¹ Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

² Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

³ Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

⁴ Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

⁵ Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

⁶ Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

⁷ Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

⁸ Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

⁹ Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

Abstract:

The current study aimed to identify the impact of the paramedic's commitment to the controls of patience and commitment on the feeling of comfort and satisfaction among recipients of medical services by formulating a questionnaire form and distributing it to a sample of 400 paramedics in the Saudi Red Crescent. It is based on a set of basic axes and items that aim to know the importance of the paramedic's commitment to patience and its impact in alleviating the suffering of patients and increasing their confidence and reassurance. The study also indicated that the moral integrity of the paramedic affects the increase in the quality of medical services provided by measuring patient satisfaction after receiving services, which helps in identifying the paramedics' shortcomings. The study presented a set of recommendations, the most important and prominent of which is the need to focus on calming patients, which increases their satisfaction rates with the health services provided, and also the need for the paramedic to contribute to creating a work environment characterized by efficiency and humanity.

Key words : First aid, ethics, commitment, patience, reassurance of patients

Corresponding author:**Saeed Ahmed alzahrani,**

Technician Emergency Medical services, Saudi Red Crescent - Al-Baha

QR code

Please cite this article in press Saeed Ahmed alzahrani et al., *The Effect Of Adherence To The Controls Of Patience And Commitment By The Paramedic On The Feeling Of Comfort And Satisfaction Among Recipients Of Therapeutic Services.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (10).

INTRODUCTION:

The commitment of the paramedic to the principles of patience and dedication is one of the most important factors that contribute to alleviating the patient's suffering and enhancing their trust in the medical services provided. When a patient faces an emergency situation, they are often in a state of anxiety and fear. The presence of a patient, understanding paramedic provides them with a sense of safety and reassurance. This is also a fundamental aspect of delivering therapeutic services in emergency cases and has a profound impact on the recipient's sense of comfort and satisfaction.^{1,15}

Ethical integrity is one of the most important qualities that paramedics should possess, as it forms the backbone of the trust built between the paramedic and the patient, as well as between the paramedic and society as a whole. The paramedic is not merely a provider of medical services but a symbol of hope and reassurance during times of crisis. Integrity is what secures this vital role; the paramedic is a symbol of trust and safety that people turn to in times of crisis. The importance of ethical integrity among paramedics lies in mutual trust, as integrity fosters a relationship based on trust between the paramedic and the patient, which helps create a safe and comfortable environment for the patient and facilitates the treatment process.^{16,9}

Moreover, integrity is closely linked to the quality of the services provided. An honest paramedic always strives to offer the best they can for the benefit of the patient. The ethical integrity of paramedics enhances the reputation of the emergency medical profession, increases community trust in its services, and reflects the professional commitment and ethical values that a paramedic should embody. Additionally, ethical integrity reflects the paramedic's commitment to human values such as compassion, empathy, and humanity. One manifestation of ethical integrity among paramedics is the maintenance of confidentiality, respecting the patient's privacy, safeguarding their personal and medical information, and adhering to professional duties without exploiting circumstances for personal gain.^{2,7,15}

Equity in dealing with patients, non-discrimination among them, awareness of the importance of life, respect for human dignity and rights, and working to save lives with all available strength are paramount. Therefore, ethical integrity among paramedics can be enhanced through regular training and the provision of comprehensive training programs that cover the ethical and professional aspects of paramedic work.

Additionally, providing leaders and role models for paramedics who exemplify ethical behavior and professionalism is essential, along with the evaluation of ethical performance. Incorporating ethical behavior assessment into the performance evaluation system for paramedics is crucial, as is establishing safe mechanisms for reporting any ethical violations without fear of retaliation. It is also important to build a strong institutional culture based on ethical and professional values and to enforce strict laws against violations of professional ethics.^{4,7,6}

One of the challenges facing ethical integrity among paramedics is psychological pressure, as paramedics often experience significant psychological stress that may affect their ability to make sound decisions. Furthermore, the high volume of work can lead to the neglect of certain ethical aspects, and paramedics may face material temptations that could compromise their integrity. Nevertheless, ethical integrity is a fundamental pillar of the paramedic profession and serves as a true guarantee for providing high-quality humanitarian services. By enhancing ethical integrity among paramedics, a more efficient and effective emergency medical system can be built, one that earns the trust of the community.^{2,3,7}

Patience and commitment are among the most important qualities that paramedics must possess, as they form the foundation for building a trusting relationship with patients and achieving the best outcomes in emergency work. The importance of patience and commitment in the work of a paramedic lies in their ability to alleviate anxiety and stress, as patients and their families often experience high levels of anxiety and tension in emergency situations. The paramedic's patience and calmness help to soothe them.^{1,16}

DISCUSSION:

The paramedic is considered the first person to interact with an injured individual in an emergency situation. Establishing a relationship built on trust and respect contributes to the patient's cooperation. Additionally, adherence to medical protocols and instructions leads to the provision of more efficient and safe medical services. Patience and commitment in emergency work are fundamental pillars for the success of any emergency team for several reasons .

Firstly, the high-pressure environment in which paramedics operate requires them to make quick and decisive decisions in critical situations. Patience helps them maintain calm and focus even in the most challenging conditions. Patients who are injured or

experiencing medical emergencies are often in states of fear and pain; thus, patience and kindness in dealing with them help to soothe and provide the necessary care. Furthermore, patients and their families may be in a state of panic and fear, necessitating that the paramedic exercise patience and effective communication to reassure and provide psychological support.15,12

Moreover, emergency work requires the collaboration and teamwork of all members, with adherence to schedules and responsibilities ensuring the smooth and effective operation of services. Therefore, the primary objective of emergency work is to save lives and provide the best possible medical care to patients. Patience and commitment are among the most important factors contributing to achieving this goal.11,8,10

The significance of commitment lies in the fact that emergency work demands high accuracy in task performance, as any error could lead to severe consequences. Adhering to established instructions and procedures ensures the provision of safe and effective medical care. Paramedics feel a significant responsibility for the lives of patients, and their commitment to their duties enables them to bear this responsibility. The field of emergency medical services requires continuous development of knowledge and skills, and a commitment to ongoing learning helps paramedics provide the best possible care for patients.1,7,4

Examples of the Importance of Patience and Commitment in Emergency Medical Work

Traffic accidents require patience and organization, as paramedics must work as a cohesive team to provide first aid to a large number of injured individuals in a short period. During natural disasters such as earthquakes and floods, intense efforts from paramedics are necessary as they operate under challenging conditions to provide relief to those affected. Additionally, handling infectious diseases requires special precautions to ensure the safety of both paramedics and patients, as well as adherence to preventive measures.2,3,5

There are negative consequences associated with a lack of patience and commitment among paramedics. For instance, impatience may increase the suffering and anxiety of the injured person. Furthermore, stress and anxiety resulting from poor treatment can lead to a deterioration of the patient's health condition. Negative behavior from paramedics can also harm the relationship with the patient and their family,

contribute to a negative perception of emergency medical services. Consequently, patience and commitment enhance the quality of care provided, foster trust with patients, and elevate the status of the paramedic profession. Moreover, a paramedic's adherence to the principles of patience and commitment is fundamental to achieving patient satisfaction and alleviating suffering in emergency situations.4,2

Thus, patience and commitment are essential traits in emergency medical work, aiding paramedics in delivering the best healthcare to patients and effectively managing difficult situations. They significantly contribute to improving the quality of medical services provided, increasing recipient satisfaction, and building a trusting relationship between the paramedic and the patient. Adhering to the principles of patience and commitment among paramedics is a key factor in enhancing the quality of healthcare.6,13

-Providing High-Quality Services for Therapeutic Cases

Providing high-quality services for therapeutic cases is a fundamental goal in any healthcare facility. It significantly contributes to improving patient health, increasing their trust in the services offered, and achieving better therapeutic outcomes. The quality of healthcare services relies on an integrated set of elements that interact to ensure the delivery of effective, safe, and appropriate healthcare for patients.1,5

These elements can be outlined as follows:

- Professional Competence: This is one of the most important elements that contribute to ensuring the quality of healthcare services. It represents the ability to perform assigned tasks with precision and high efficiency while adhering to professional and ethical standards. The importance of professional competence in the healthcare field lies in its contribution to providing high-quality care for patients, which leads to improved treatment outcomes and reduced complications. It also helps to increase trust in healthcare services. When patients observe competence and professionalism in their interactions, it enhances their confidence in the healthcare system as a whole. Additionally, professional competence aids in reducing medical errors, thereby protecting patient health and minimizing financial and human losses. In emergency situations, professional competence plays a crucial role in delivering first aid and making quick and accurate decisions. It encourages the pursuit of new methods to improve healthcare services and the

adoption of modern technologies. Key components of professional competence in the healthcare field include scientific knowledge, where the healthcare provider must have extensive knowledge of modern medical information and techniques used in their field, practical skills, where they should be able to apply theoretical knowledge in practical settings, perform medical examinations and procedures with precision and skill. They should also possess high communication skills.^{12,13}

To interact with patients and their families, as well as the healthcare team, and to convey information clearly and simply, it is essential to adhere to the highest ethical standards in dealing with patients, respecting their privacy and dignity. Additionally, there should be a willingness to continuously develop skills and knowledge through attending training courses and staying updated on the latest developments in the health field. To enhance professional competence in healthcare, it is crucial to encourage healthcare staff to participate in training courses and workshops to develop their skills, provide a safe and motivating work environment, and ensure the necessary resources are available for efficient job performance. Regular evaluation of healthcare staff performance should be conducted to identify strengths and weaknesses and provide necessary feedback. Healthcare personnel should also be encouraged to participate in scientific research to advance knowledge in the health field and apply quality standards across all healthcare facilities to ensure the provision of high-quality health services.^{14,3}

Thus, professional competence is considered one of the most important elements to focus on in the healthcare field, as it significantly contributes to improving the quality of services provided and ensuring the health and safety of patients. All healthcare practitioners must strive to continuously develop their professional competence by taking advantage of various available opportunities.^{2,6}

-Patient-Centered Focus: The patient is the focal point of the entire healthcare process, and focusing efforts on meeting their needs and desires is fundamental to ensuring the quality of health services. When the patient is at the center of attention, it leads to an improved health experience, increased trust in the healthcare system, and better therapeutic outcomes. A patient-centered focus is a comprehensive approach that places the needs and desires of the patient at the core of the healthcare delivery process. It involves encouraging the patient to participate in decision-making regarding their care.^{2,4}

The patient's involvement in decision-making regarding their health, along with providing the necessary information for making informed decisions, is crucial for delivering specialized medical care and designing individualized treatment plans that suit each patient while considering their health, psychological, and social circumstances. Establishing a strong relationship based on trust and respect between the patient and healthcare provider, along with continuous and clear communication with the patient and their family, is essential for clarifying all information related to the patient's health condition and treatment.^{1,5,7}

The importance of patient-centered focus is evident; when patients feel that their needs are prioritized, it significantly enhances their health experience and increases adherence to treatment plans. Patients who feel cared for are more likely to comply with prescribed treatment regimens. Additionally, focusing on the patient helps reduce complaints and disputes between patients and healthcare providers. When patients are satisfied with the healthcare services provided, it reinforces their trust in the healthcare system as a whole.^{8,2}

One of the dimensions of patient-centered care is involving patients in decision-making. Patients should be included in decisions regarding their health as much as possible. Communication between the patient and healthcare provider must be clear and direct, utilizing simple and understandable language. Respecting the patient and valuing their opinions and feelings is essential, as is maintaining the privacy and security of the patient's personal information.^{1,8,9}

Methods to implement patient-centered care include training healthcare workers on the importance of patient focus and how to apply it in practical settings, as well as educating patients about their rights and responsibilities and how to engage in the healthcare process. Regular assessments of patient satisfaction with the provided healthcare services should be conducted, alongside the application of effective communication techniques and efforts to create a comfortable and safe environment for patients during their stay in healthcare facilities.^{9,12,1}

-The Impact of Commitment by Paramedics on Comfort and Satisfaction of Service Recipients

The commitment of paramedics to their professional roles and work ethics has a direct impact on the comfort and satisfaction of medical service recipients. This commitment goes beyond providing first aid to building a trusting relationship with the patient and

creating a comfortable medical environment. One of the positive effects of paramedic commitment is the feeling of safety; when a patient feels that the paramedic is dedicated to their duty and cares about their health and comfort, they experience a sense of security and trust, which helps them relax and accept medical procedures. Additionally, positive and professional interactions from the paramedic aid in alleviating the anxiety and stress that the patient or their family may experience in emergency situations. When the experience with the paramedic is positive, it leaves a good impression on the patient, contributing to an improved overall experience with medical services and a perception that the care received was good and professional, thus increasing patient satisfaction with the medical services provided. 4,1,8 Furthermore, building a trusting relationship between the paramedic and the patient facilitates better information exchange, which assists in delivering appropriate medical care.9

Therefore, paramedics can enhance their commitment by undergoing continuous training programs to develop their skills and medical knowledge, periodically assessing paramedic performance to identify strengths and weaknesses, and implementing necessary actions for performance improvement. It is also essential to activate a reward program for paramedics based on their efforts and achievements, promoting positive behaviors and fostering a cohesive teamwork environment based on collaboration and mutual respect.8,2

The commitment of paramedics to their duties is considered the cornerstone of achieving patient satisfaction and providing high-quality medical services. By building trust, alleviating anxiety, and enhancing the patient experience, paramedics contribute to the establishment of a more efficient and humane healthcare system. They help create emergency response teams capable of delivering high-quality medical care that meets patients' needs, as the commitment of paramedics to their professional roles significantly impacts the quality of medical services provided.10,11

METHODS:

The current research relies on the descriptive and analytical approach as a fundamental pillar of scientific research, and its methodology is considered one of the most important methods employed. A researcher seeking reliable scientific results must ensure to describe the current state of the phenomenon by observing it and elucidating and understanding its content. Subsequently, they must obtain accurate and detailed descriptions in order to answer the questions they pose and the problems they study. The study focused on the research community, which is the Saudi Red Crescent, and drew a random sample consisting of 400 paramedics.

Design:

The questionnaire was designed based on the objectives of the current research, which focus on:

- Measuring the impact of the paramedic's commitment on alleviating patient suffering.

- Measuring the impact of the paramedic's commitment on increasing patient trust.

- Measuring the effect of good handling during emergencies on reassuring patients.

- Measuring the impact of ethical integrity in paramedics on enhancing the quality of medical services provided.

- Measuring the effect of understanding patient satisfaction after receiving services to identify paramedic shortcomings.

- Measuring the impact of focusing on calming patients to increase their satisfaction rates with the provided health services.

- Measuring the paramedic's contribution to creating a work environment characterized by efficiency and humanity.

Study setting

The questionnaire was distributed electronically to a sample of paramedics working with the Saudi Red Crescent during the period from July 2024 to August 2024, with a sample size of 400 paramedics.

RESULTS:**Characteristics of study participants:**

Table 1.0 The commitment of the paramedic to patience alleviates the suffering of patients. Age

The commitment of the paramedic to patience alleviates the suffering of patients.	percentage	Repetitions
Strongly agree	32.5%	130
Agree	37.5%	150
Neutral	17.5%	100
Disagree	20%	20
Strongly Disagree	0%	0
total	100%	400

Figer1.0 : The commitment of the paramedic to patience alleviates the suffering of patients.

The figure illustrates the sample responses regarding the paramedic's commitment to patience, which alleviates the patient's suffering. This is due to the fact that patients in emergency situations experience increased psychological and emotional stress that affects their ability to endure pain or distress. The paramedic's commitment to patience is considered one of the most important methods for alleviating patients' suffering.

Table 2.0 The paramedic's adherence to commitment increases patient trust.

The paramedic's adherence to commitment increases patient trust.	percentage	Repetitions
Strongly agree	52.5%	210
Agree	35%	140
Neutral	10%	40
Disagree	0%	0
Strongly Disagree	52.5%	210
total	100%	400

Figer2.0 : The paramedic's adherence to commitment increases patient trust.

The figure illustrates the sample responses regarding the commitment of the paramedic to adherence, which increases patient confidence. This is due to the fact that patients in emergency situations experience a greater loss of trust, and at this moment, they seek to enhance their feelings of confidence in the paramedic. The paramedic's commitment to good ethics and kind words is one of the sources of gaining patient trust in emergency situations.

Table 3.0 Good handling in emergency situations reassures patients.

Good handling in emergency situations reassures patients.	percentage	Repetitions
Strongly agree	52.5%	210
Agree	35%	140
Neutral	10%	40
Disagree	0%	0
Strongly Disagree	0%	0
total	100%	400

Figer3.0 : Good handling in emergency situations reassures patients.

The figure illustrates the sample responses regarding the good handling of emergencies, which reassures patients. This is due to the fact that patients in emergency situations experience a greater loss of trust, and at this moment, they seek to enhance their feelings of confidence in the responder. The responder's commitment to good ethics and kind words is one of the sources of gaining patients' trust in emergency situations.

Table 4.0 Ethical integrity in the paramedic affects the enhancement of the quality of medical services provided.

Ethical integrity in the paramedic affects the enhancement of the quality of medical services provided .	percentage	Repetitions
Strongly agree	25%	100
Agree	37.5%	150
Neutral	17.5%	70
Disagree	20%	80
Strongly Disagree	0%	0
total	100%	400

Figer4.0 Ethical integrity in the paramedic affects the enhancement of the quality of medical services provided.

The figure illustrates that the sample's responses regarding the paramedic's ethical integrity influence the enhancement of the quality of medical services provided. This is due to the fact that patients in emergency situations experience a greater loss of trust, and at that moment, they seek to increase their feelings of confidence in the paramedic. The paramedic's commitment to good ethics and kind words is one of the sources of gaining trust from patients in emergency situations.

Table 5.0 : Measuring patient satisfaction after receiving services helps identify the shortcomings of paramedics.

Measuring patient satisfaction after receiving services helps identify the shortcomings of paramedics.	percentage	Repetitions
Strongly agree	20%	80
Agree	62.5%	250
Neutral	12.5%	50
Disagree	5%	20
Strongly Disagree	0	0
total	100%	400

Fig5.0 Measuring patient satisfaction after receiving services helps identify the shortcomings of paramedics.

The figure illustrates the sample responses to the patient satisfaction measurement item after receiving services, which helps identify the shortcomings of the paramedics. This is particularly important as patients in emergency situations experience a greater loss of trust, and at that moment, they desire to enhance their feelings of confidence in the paramedic. The significance of measuring their satisfaction with the services provided after receiving them lies in its ability to indicate the extent of their impact by the paramedic's commitment and to identify their satisfaction rates.

Table 6.0 : Focusing on calming patients increases their satisfaction rates with the healthcare services provided.

Focusing on calming patients increases their satisfaction rates with the healthcare services provided .	percentage	Repetitions
Strongly agree	37.5%	150
Agree	20%	80
Neutral	22.5%	90
Disagree	20%	80
Strongly Disagree	0%	0
total	100%	400

Figur 6.0 : Focusing on calming patients increases their satisfaction rates with the healthcare services provided.

The figure illustrates the sample responses to the item indicating that focusing on calming patients increases their satisfaction rates with the provided healthcare services. This is due to the fact that patients in emergency situations experience greater loss of tension and anxiety, and at that moment, they desire to enhance feelings of calmness, comfort, and safety. This responsibility falls on the paramedic.

Table 7.0 : The paramedic contributes to creating a work environment characterized by efficiency and humanity.

The paramedic contributes to creating a work environment characterized by efficiency and humanity.	percentage	Repetitions
Strongly agree	40%	160
Agree	37.5 %	150
Neutral	22.5%	90
Disagree	0%	0
Strongly Disagree	0%	0
total	100%	400

Figure 7.0 : The paramedic contributes to creating a work environment characterized by efficiency and humanity.

The figure shows the sample responses to the item measuring the paramedic's contribution to creating an efficient and humane work environment through joint cooperation between paramedics and each other and working to create a balanced environment of teamwork whose main goal is to focus on the patient, provide him with his needs, reassure him, and increase his levels of feeling satisfied.

Table: 3,0 the mean, standard deviation, and relative importance of sample responses:

The item	The mean	Standard deviation	relative
The commitment of the paramedic to patience alleviates the suffering of patients.	4.05	0.918	%80.00
The paramedic's adherence to commitment increases patient trust.	3.96	1.023	%87.24
Good handling in emergency situations reassures patients.	3.67	1.398	%69.13
Ethical integrity in the paramedic affects the enhancement of the quality of medical services provided.	4.5	1.363	%98.24
Measuring patient satisfaction after receiving services helps identify the shortcomings of paramedics.	3.46	0.668	%88.11
Focusing on calming patients increases their satisfaction rates with the healthcare services provided.	3.54	0.922	%70.89
The paramedic contributes to creating a work environment characterized by efficiency and humanity.	4.5	1.363	%98.24

The results related to the study indicated that there is a statistically significant effect of the paramedic's adherence to patience and commitment on the sense of comfort and satisfaction among recipients of therapeutic services. This was determined after measuring the mean and standard deviation of the sample responses regarding the questionnaire, highlighting the importance of the paramedic exhibiting patience when receiving requests from patients and the necessity of instilling principles of ethical and value-based commitment among paramedics.

There are numerous methods to evaluate the quality of healthcare services. These include conducting surveys of patients and staff to measure their satisfaction with the services provided, reviewing medical records to assess the quality of care delivered to patients, and utilizing qualitative indicators to measure performance in various areas such as hospital-acquired infection rates and mortality rates. Experts evaluate healthcare institutions according to specific standards. However, some challenges exist in quality assessment, including resource shortages, as some healthcare institutions may face a lack of necessary resources to implement

quality assessment programs. Additionally, some staff may resist change, hindering the quality evaluation process, and measuring certain qualitative aspects of healthcare, such as patient psychological satisfaction, can be difficult.

Therefore, quality assessment is an ongoing process that requires commitment from all personnel within the healthcare institution. Through periodic quality evaluations, healthcare institutions can improve their performance and provide high-quality health services that meet patients' needs and expectations.

As previously mentioned, delivering high-quality healthcare services is a shared responsibility among all healthcare professionals. By adhering to the fundamental principles of quality, better healthcare can be provided to patients, thereby improving their quality of life. The importance of quality in healthcare is linked to patient satisfaction, which leads to increased trust in the healthcare institution and a rise in patient numbers. It also contributes to improved patient health and faster recovery, reduces medical errors, avoids complications, enhances the institution's reputation, and makes it more competitive.

CONCLUSION:

This study focuses on measuring the impact of the paramedic's commitment to the principles of patience and adherence on the sense of comfort and satisfaction among recipients of therapeutic services. It emphasizes that the patient is at the core of quality healthcare services, leading to improved quality of life for patients and increased satisfaction with the services provided. All healthcare professionals must place the patient at the center of their attention and strive to meet their needs and desires. Consequently, cultivating patience is essential, along with possessing effective communication skills to interact with patients, their families, and the healthcare team, conveying information clearly and simply. They must adhere to the highest ethical standards in dealing with patients, respecting their privacy and dignity. Additionally, there should be a continuous desire to enhance skills and knowledge through attending training courses and staying updated on the latest developments in the healthcare field.

To enhance professional competence in healthcare, it is crucial to encourage health personnel to attend training courses and workshops to develop their skills, provide a safe and motivating work environment, and ensure the necessary resources are available for efficient work performance. Regular evaluation of healthcare personnel's performance is essential to identify strengths and weaknesses, provide necessary feedback, and encourage participation in scientific research to advance knowledge in the healthcare field. Implementing quality standards across all healthcare facilities is also vital to ensure the provision of high-quality health services.

Thus, professional competence is one of the most important elements to focus on in healthcare, as it significantly contributes to improving the quality of services provided and ensuring the health and safety of patients. All healthcare practitioners should continuously strive to develop their professional competence by taking advantage of available opportunities

Patient-Centered Care: The patient is considered the focal point of the entire healthcare process, and focusing efforts on meeting their needs and desires is fundamental to ensuring the quality of health services. When the patient is at the center of attention, it leads to an improved health experience, increased trust in the healthcare system, and better treatment outcomes. Patient-centered care is a comprehensive approach that places the needs and desires of the patient at the core of healthcare delivery. It involves encouraging

patients to participate in decision-making regarding their health, providing the necessary information for them to make informed choices, offering specialized medical care, and designing individualized treatment plans that suit each patient while considering their health, psychological, and social circumstances.

Building a strong relationship based on trust and respect between the patient and healthcare provider is essential, along with continuous and clear communication with the patient and their family, clarifying all information related to their health condition and treatment. The importance of patient-centered care is evident; when patients feel prioritized, their health experience significantly improves, and their adherence to the treatment plan increases. Patients who feel cared for are more likely to comply with the prescribed treatment plan. Furthermore, focusing on the patient helps reduce complaints and disputes between the patient and the healthcare provider. When patients are satisfied with the health services provided to them, it enhances their overall trust in the healthcare system.

One aspect of patient-centered care is shared decision-making, where patients should be involved in decisions regarding their health as much as possible. Communication between the patient and healthcare provider should be clear and direct, using simple and understandable language. Patients' opinions and feelings should be respected and valued, and it is essential to maintain the patient's privacy and the security of their personal information.

The therapeutic environment plays a crucial role in achieving the quality of healthcare services. When the therapeutic environment is comfortable, safe, and stimulating, it contributes to improving patient health and well-being, as well as enhancing their confidence in the healthcare system. Therefore, all healthcare professionals should strive to improve the therapeutic environment in the healthcare institutions where they work.

Quality assessment is a systematic process for measuring the extent to which healthcare services meet previously established standards. It serves as a compass that guides healthcare institutions toward improving their performance and delivering high-quality health services. Quality assessment is a fundamental element in ensuring patient satisfaction, increasing resource efficiency, and improving health outcomes. The importance of quality assessment lies in enhancing the quality of healthcare, as it helps identify strengths and weaknesses in health services,

enabling necessary actions to improve quality. Quality assessment aids healthcare institutions in determining their needs and expectations, allowing for better fulfillment. It also helps identify common medical errors and implement necessary preventive measures, as well as pinpoint ineffective processes and find ways to improve them, leading to increased efficiency and reduced costs.

Quality assessment encompasses a wide range of aspects, including the quality of services provided, where the appropriateness of services for patient needs, their effectiveness, and safety are evaluated. Patient satisfaction with the provided health services is also measured through surveys and interviews. Resource efficiency is assessed by evaluating the effectiveness of the use of available resources such as devices, equipment, and medical staff. Additionally, the safety of the therapeutic environment and the application of preventive measures to prevent medical errors are also evaluated.

REFERENCES:

- 1- Wang, W., Zhang, J., Lu, J., & Wei, X. (2023). Patient views of the good doctor in primary care: a qualitative study in six provinces in China. *Global Health Research and Policy*, 8(1), 24.
- 2- Chen, G. (2023). The effective reduction of violence against doctors through the improvement of medical humanistic care. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, 1403-1407.
- 3- Kumar, D., Sinha, T., Paul, S. K., Chowdhury, P. D., & Pal, R. (2021). Doctor-patient communication among interns at a tertiary care medical college and hospital in eastern India.
- 4- Davis, K., Carbone, R., Fredericks, J., Lujan, J., & Basdeo, A. (2021). What makes a good doctor: a qualitative study of patient perspectives.
- 5- Collings-Hughes, D., Townsend, R., & Williams, B. (2023). Paramedic use and understanding of their professional code of conduct. *Nursing ethics*, 30(2), 258-275.
- 6- Aung, K. T. (2024). Ethical Considerations in Emergency Medical Services (EMS): Understanding the Significance of Confidentiality-A Scoping Review. *Asian Journal of Medicine and Health Sciences* Vol, 7(1), 5.
- 7- Cook, A. L., Capsey, M., Jones, C., Davidson, T., & Eaton, G. (2023). Discussing values in paramedic practice. *Journal of Paramedic Practice*, 15(4), 165-169.
- 8- Campbell, I., Hill, L., & Copson, J. (2024). Towards an understanding of the embedded nature of everyday ethical reasoning in paramedic education and practice. *Paramedicine*, 27536386241252856.
- 9- Milling, L. (2023). Decision-making in prehospital resuscitation: The ethical aspects of out-of-hospital cardiac arrest treatment.
- 10- Serikovna-Seitkazina, K., Burzakhanov, M. M., Yumashev, A. V., Dokhmila, D. V., Marshalova, V. A., & Markov, A. A. (2023). Ensuring The Quality of Healthcare Services in Medicine and Dentistry: The Role of Medical Education, Regulatory Requirements and Effective Practices. *Journal of Complementary Medicine Research*, 14(3), 229-232.
- 11- Llana, A. J. O., Ruiz, J. A. Z., & Claudio, B. A. M. (2023). Quality of service and citizen satisfaction in a Lima district municipality. *Southern perspective/Perspectiva austral*, 1, 17-17.
- 12- Azzahra, S. N., Pratiwi, S. D., Yusuf, M., & Pasaribu, U. R. (2024, June). Legal Protection of Medical Personnel in The Resolution of Medical Disputes According to Health Law Number 17 of 2023. In *Proceedings: International Forum Research on Education, Social Sciences Technology and Humanities* (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 324-330).
- 13- Li, H., Yazdi, M., Huang, H. Z., Huang, C. G., Peng, W., Nedjati, A., & Adesina, K. A. (2023). A fuzzy rough copula Bayesian network model for solving complex hospital service quality assessment. *Complex & Intelligent Systems*, 9(5), 5527-5553.
- 14- Adamopoulos, I. P., & Syrou, N. F. (2023). Administration safety and occupational risks relationship with job position training quality and needs of medical public health services workforce correlated by political leadership interventions. *Electronic Journal of Medical & Educational Technologies*, 16(3).
- 15- Maguire, B. J., Maniscalco, P. M., & Cormier, S. B. (2024). Creating the Emergency Medical Services System of the Future: the role of the EMS Education Agenda.
- 16- Uysal, İ., Korkmaz, G., & Toraman, Ç. (2024). The relationship between ambulance team's professional commitment, occupational anxiety, and resilience levels. *BMC health services research*, 24(1), 716.

Pursuit:

Dear paramedic, the current research aims to reveal the impact of the paramedic's adherence to the principles of patience and commitment on the sense of comfort and satisfaction among recipients of therapeutic services. It is important to note that all data mentioned in the questionnaire is kept completely confidential and is intended solely for scientific research purposes.

- The commitment of the paramedic to patience alleviates the suffering of patients .

Strongly agree ()
Agree ()
Neutral ()
Disagree ()
Strongly disagree ()
- The paramedic's adherence to commitment increases patient trust .

Strongly agree ()
Agree ()
Neutral ()
Disagree ()
Strongly disagree ()
- Good handling in emergency situations reassures patients .

Strongly agree ()
Agree ()
Neutral ()
Disagree ()
Strongly disagree ()
- Ethical integrity in the paramedic affects the enhancement of the quality of medical services provided .

Strongly agree ()
Agree ()
Neutral ()
Disagree ()
Strongly disagree ()
- Measuring patient satisfaction after receiving services helps identify the shortcomings of paramedics .

Strongly agree ()
Agree ()
Neutral ()
Disagree ()
Strongly disagree ()
- Focusing on calming patients increases their satisfaction rates with the healthcare services provided .

Strongly agree ()
Agree ()
Neutral ()
Disagree ()
Strongly disagree()

- The paramedic contributes to creating a work environment characterized by efficiency and humanity.

Strongly agree ()

Agree ()

Neutral ()

Disagree ()

Strongly disagree ()